

Organic corrosion inhibitors for copper and brass — A review

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Abstract : The literature dealing with the corrosion of copper and brass and their prevention using organic inhibitors is examined. The inhibition efficiency of an organic molecule depends on several factors and some of them are the shape, aromaticity, bond strength to metal substrate, the presence of hetero atom and number of bonding atoms or groups. Several new inhibitors have been synthesized and attempts have been made to correlate the inhibition efficiency with these factors. Azoles, Schiff bases, amides, amino acids are found to be good corrosion inhibitors for copper and brass in acidic solution. These compounds as well as several imidazoline and hydropyrimidine derivatives can inhibit corrosion of copper and brass satisfactorily in neutral medium containing chloride ions. In alkaline solution compounds containing -SH group may be good inhibitors. Temperature, pH and stability in the aggressive media are also factors related to the efficiency of the inhibitor. Now research area is oriented to the development of green corrosion inhibitors and work on amino acids and their derivatives is increasing.

Keywords : Amino acids, azoles, brass, copper, corrosion inhibitors, hydropyrimidines, imidazolines.

Introduction

Copper and its alloys are extensively used due to electrical, thermal, mechanical and corrosion resistance properties. However, in the presence of oxygen, chloride, sulphate and nitrate ions they are exposed to localized corrosion¹. One current approach to protect metals and alloys against corrosion is the use of inhibitors. Amongst them there are inorganic inhibitors. Manganate— MnO_4^- , chromate— CrO_4^{2-} , molybdate— MoO_4^{2-} , tetraborate— $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and phosphate— PO_4^{3-} are useful²⁻⁴. But large number of organic compounds such as azoles, amines, Schiff bases, imidazolines, hydropyrimidines, amino acids etc. are useful corrosion inhibitors in acidic, neutral and alkaline media. Depending on the structure, they act as a protective layer formed by physisorption in the metal/electrolyte interphase or as an insoluble chelate barrier developed by chemisorptions which avoid direct contact of the metal/alloy with the aggressive media⁵. The ability of an organic molecule to inhibit metal corrosion depends on several factors and some of them are shape, branching or conformation, aromaticity, conjugation, bond strength to metal substrate, the presence of nitrogen, oxygen and or sulphur atoms and number of bonding groups or atoms. Temperature, pH and stability in the aggressive media

are also factors related to the efficiency of the inhibitor^{6,7}.

There are many techniques that can be used in the laboratory for testing inhibition efficiency. These are :

- (a) Weight loss method⁸,
- (b) Potentiodynamic polarization method⁸,
- (c) Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy⁸,
- (d) Scanning electron microscopy⁹,
- (e) Energy dispersive X-ray investigation⁹,
- (f) Quantum chemistry and molecular mechanics method¹⁰.

Organic corrosion inhibitors

Corrosion inhibition studies of copper and brass may be classified into three types depending on the medium, viz. acidic, neutral and alkaline. Table 1 shows the molecular structure of various compounds and their inhibition efficiency.

Corrosion inhibition of copper and brass in acidic medium :

Behpour *et al.*¹¹ studied the effect of Schiff bases on the corrosion of copper in 15% hydrochloric acid. The

Table 1. Molecular structure and inhibition efficiency of various inhibitors

Structure	Name	Type of inhibitor	Concentration	Metal/ alloys	Medium	Efficiency (%)
	2-Amino-5-(ethylthio)-1,3,4-thiadiazole ⁹	Mixed	1×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	3% NaCl	90.0
	Bis-(1-benzotriazolyl)methylene)-(2,5-thiadiazolyl)-disulphide ¹⁶	Mixed	1×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	3% NaCl	87.6
	Benzotriazole ¹⁸	Anodic	1×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	0.5 M NaCl	26.2
	2-Mercaptobenzoxazole ¹⁸	Anodic	1×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	0.5 M HCl	35.0
	2-Mercaptobenzimidazole ¹⁸	Anodic	1×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	0.5 M HCl	91.6
	Benzotriazole ⁴³	Mixed	1.2×10^{-3} (M)	Brass	3% NaCl	77.4
	1-Hydroxymethylbenzotriazole ⁴³	Mixed	1×10^{-3} (M)	Brass	3% NaCl	93.4
	N-[(1-Benzotriazol-1-yl)-methyl]aniline ⁴³	Mixed	2×10^{-4} (M)	Brass	3% NaCl	59.8
	N,N-Dibenzotriazol-1-yl-methylaminomethane ⁴³	Mixed	5.6×10^{-4} (M)	Brass	Sea water	88.1

Table-1 (contd.)

	3-Hydroxypropylbenzotriazole ⁴³	Mixed	8.4×10^{-4} (M)	Brass	Sea water	91.1
	N-[(1-Benzotriazol-1-yl)ethyl]aniline ⁴³	Mixed	6.3×10^{-4} (M)	Brass	3% NaCl	90.4
	N,N'-Dibenzotriazol-1-yl methylaminoethane ⁴³	Mixed	5.3×10^{-4} (M)	Brass	3% NaCl	93.5
	2-[(Pyridin-2-ylimino)methyl]-phenol ⁴⁹	Mixed	9.6×10^{-4} (M)	Brass	3% NaCl	87.0
	2-[(Pyridin-2-ylamino)methyl]-phenol ⁴⁹	Mixed	9.47×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	3% NaCl	85.5
$(C_2H_5)_2N-CH_2-CHOH-CH_2-N(C_2H_5)_2$	1,3-Bis-diethylaminopropan-2-ol ⁵¹	Anodic	1×10^{-2} (M)	Brass	Water	92.5
	1,5-Bis(4-dithio-carboxylate-1-dodecyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylpyrazolyl)pentane ⁵⁰	Mixed	Coated with 100 g/L solution	Brass	3.5% NaCl	92.7

Table-1 (contd.)

	Mixed	1.6×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	1.5% HCl	95.9
	Mixed	1.3×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	1.5% HCl	96.8
Benzotriazole ¹¹	Mixed	5×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	3% NaCl	38.5
1-Hydroxybenzotriazole ⁴²	Mixed	5×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	3% NaCl	89.3
Indole-2-carboxylic acid ²⁷	Mixed	1×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	97.0
Aspartic acid ¹⁷	Mixed	1×10^{-2} (M)	Copper	0.5 M HCl	56.9
Glutamic acid ¹⁷	Mixed	1×10^{-2} (M)	Copper	0.5 M HCl	59.7
Asparagine ¹⁷	Mixed	1×10^{-1} (M)	Copper	0.5 M HCl	65.3
Glutamine ¹⁷	Mixed	1×10^{-1} (M)	Copper	0.5 M HCl	73.5

Table-1 (contd.)

Adenine ⁵⁹	Mixed	1×10^{-2} (M)	Copper	1 M NaCl	92.0
Sodium dodecylbenzenesulphonate ²⁵	Mixed	4×10^{-3} (M)	Copper	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	76.0
2-Mercaptobenzoxazole ²⁵	Mixed	3×10^{-4} (M)	Copper	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	95.0
2-Mercaptobenzothiazole ⁴⁶ and Tween 20 (150 ppm)	Mixed	1×10^{-3} (M)	Brass	0.2 M NaCl	94.0
1-[N,N-Bis(hydroxyethyl)amino-methyl]-benzotriazole ²⁶	Mixed	5×10^{-4} (M)	Brass	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	61.5
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid ⁷⁷	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	55.6
<i>o</i> -Benzenesulphonamido-benzoic acid ⁷⁷	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	67.2
<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid ⁷⁷	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	73.8
<i>p</i> -Benzenesulphonamido benzoic acid ⁷⁷	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	82.4
Glycine ⁵³	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	27.3

Table-1 (contd.)

	N-Benzenesulphonylglycine ⁵³	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	45.6
	N-Benzoylglycine ⁵³	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	84.6
	Aspartic acid ⁵⁶	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	45.2
	N-Benzenesulphonyl aspartic acid ⁵⁶	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	77.3
	Glutamic acid ⁵⁶	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	56.3
	N-Benzenesulphonyl glutamic acid ⁵⁶	Mixed	4×10^{-5} (M)	Brass	0.6 M NaCl	83.4
	N-(3-Methoxyphenyl)phthalimide ³⁴	Mixed	1×10^{-4} (M)	Copper	2 M HNO ₃	93.1
	N-(3-Methylphenyl)phthalimide ³⁴	Mixed	1×10^{-4} (M)	Copper	2 M HNO ₃	80.9
	N-(Phenylaminomethyl)phthalimide ³⁴	Mixed	1×10^{-4} (M)	Copper	2 M HNO ₃	79.1
	Purine ⁶⁰	Mixed	1×10^{-2} (M)	Copper	1 M NaCl	76.0
	Caffeine ⁶¹	Mixed	1×10^{-2} (M)	Copper	0.5 M KNO ₃	60

Schiff bases used are 2-({1-methyl-3-[(2-sulphonylphenyl)imino]butylidene}amino)-1-benzenethiol and 2-({1,2-diphenyl-2-[(2-sulphonylphenyl)imino]ethylenedene}amino)-1-benzenethiol. The second compound was found to be better inhibitor. These compounds act as mixed inhibitor. Sherif *et al.* investigated the influence of 2-amino-5-ethylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazole¹², 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole¹³ and *N*-phenyl-1,4-phenylenediamine¹⁴ on copper corrosion in HCl solution. Inhibition efficiency was 78% at 10 mM concentration of 2-amino-5-ethylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazole. About 72% inhibition efficiency was observed with 5×10^{-3} M 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole concentration. *N*-Phenyl-1,4-phenylenediamine was reported to be good mixed type inhibitor for copper in de-aerated and aerated aqueous 0.5 M HCl solution (I.E. > 80%)¹⁵.

Zhang and coworkers studied the inhibition effect of copper corrosion in 0.5 M HCl solution by bis-(1-benzotriazolyl-methylene)-(2,5-thiadiazolyl)-disulfide¹⁶, aspartic acid, asparagine, glutamic acid and glutamine¹⁷ which act as a mixed type inhibitor and benzotriazole¹⁸⁻²¹, 2-mercapto benzotriazole and 3-mercapto benzimidazole¹⁸ which act as anodic inhibitors. Inhibition effect of amino acid on copper corrosion in HCl solution was studied to find out environment friendly inhibitors¹⁷. In order to introduce non-toxic organic inhibitor for copper in acidic chloride solution, cysteine was used by Ismail²². Inhibition efficiency was 84%. Presence of Cu^{2+} ion increases the inhibition efficiency to 90%. The adsorption free energy of cysteine on copper indicated strong physical adsorption of the inhibitor on the metal surface.

Zhang *et al.*²³ studied the efficiency of methionine as a non-toxic corrosion inhibitor for copper in 0.5 M HCl. Methionine showed limited inhibiting properties for copper corrosion. The presence of Zn^{2+} ion increased the inhibition efficiency to 92%. The adsorption free energy of methionine on copper indicated physical adsorption of the inhibitor on the copper surface. Recently they studied²⁴ the corrosion protection of copper by glutamic acid, cysteine, glycine and glutathione in 0.5 M HCl. Glutathione gave 96.4% inhibition efficiency at a concentration of 10 mM.

Tavakoli *et al.*²⁵ studied the synergistic effect on corrosion inhibition of copper in H_2SO_4 solution by sodium dodecylbenzenesulphonate and 2-mercapto benzotriazole.

About 95% inhibition efficiency was achieved. The effect of 1-[*N,N*-bis-(hydroxyethyl)aminomethyl]-benzotriazole on the corrosion of brass in aqueous H_2SO_4 solution was studied by Schweinsberg and coworkers²⁶. Overall inhibition increased with increasing concentration to a maximum (63.1%) at the 5×10^{-4} M level. The inhibition efficiency was comparable to that observed for benzotriazole under the same conditions.

Quartarome *et al.*²⁷ studied the inhibiting action of indole-2-carboxylic acid on the corrosion of commercial copper in aerated 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution in the temperature range 25–55 °C by weight loss, potentiodynamic and analytical test and the determination of double layer capacitance. The compound exhibited 98% inhibition efficiency. Mechanism of copper corrosion and electro dissolution in naturally aerated stagnant 0.5 M H_2SO_4 was studied by Lu and co-workers²⁸. The role of dissolved oxygen was investigated and they concluded that near to corrosion potential, corrosion rate was controlled by a combined cathodic kinetic-anodic diffusion process. Under this condition 2-mercapto-1-methylimidazole was found to good inhibitor for copper²⁹. The inhibition efficiency was 81% at 10^{-4} M concentration. The inhibitor is absorbed on the copper surface according to Langmuir adsorption isotherm model. The synergistic inhibition effect of rhodamine and iodide ion on the corrosion of copper in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution was studied by Solmaz *et al.*³⁰. It was reported that rhodamine provided satisfactory inhibition on corrosion of copper. Its inhibition efficiency was further increased in presence of iodide ion due to synergistic effect. A new guanidine derivative *N*-(5,6-diphenyl-4,5-dihydro-[1,2,4]triazin-3-yl)-guanidine was synthesized by refluxing guanidine hydrochloride with 5,6-diphenyl-4,5-dihydro[1,2,4]triazine-3-thiol in DMF for 2 h³¹. It is found to be good copper corrosion inhibitor in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution. The extract of cannabis plant was reported to be an effective inhibitor for copper corrosion under identical condition³². The inhibitor 5-mercapto-1-phenyltetrazole may be useful in controlling copper corrosion in 1 mM H_2SO_4 solution³³.

The effect of *N*-(3-methoxyphenylaminomethyl)-phthalimide (A_1); *N*-(3-methylphenylaminomethyl)-phthalimide (A_2) and *N*-(phenylaminomethyl)phthalimide (A_3) on copper corrosion in 2 M HNO_3 was investigated

by Fouda and coworkers. Inhibition efficiency decreased in the following order : $A_1 > A_2 > A_3$. As the concentration is increased its efficiency is also increased. *N*-(3-Methoxyphenylaminomethyl)phthalimide has reached the highest efficiency i.e. 93.10%. It has been observed that inhibition efficiency is higher when the compound has higher molecular weight and more centers for bonding with copper³⁴. Triazole derivatives are found to be good corrosion inhibitor for copper in nitric acid solution^{35,36}. Two newly developed triazole derivatives : bis[4-amino-5-hydroxy-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl]methane (B_1) and bis[4-amino-5-hydroxy-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl]butane (B_2) are found to be good copper corrosion inhibitors in 4.0 M HNO_3 solution. The inhibition efficiency is $>80\%$ and B_2 is more efficient than B_1 ³⁶. Tetrazole and its derivatives : 1,2,3,4-tetrazole (C_1), 5-amino-1,2,3,4-tetrazole (C_2), 1-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrazole (C_3) and 1-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,3,4-tetrazole (C_4) are reported to be good corrosion inhibitors for copper in 0.1 M HNO_3 solution. These act as mixed type inhibitors. Chemisorption of the inhibitors on the copper surface is responsible for inhibition and follows Langmuir isotherm³⁷. Inhibition efficiency increases in the following order : $C_1 < C_2 < C_3 < C_4$.

Corrosion inhibition of copper and brass in neutral medium :

Extensive work is going on the inhibition of corrosion of copper and brass in sodium chloride solution^{9,38-46}. Sherif *et al.* investigated the influence of 2-amino-5-ethylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazole³⁸, 2-amino-5-ethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole³⁹, 5-phenyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiole³⁹ and *N*-phenyl-1,4-phenylenediamine⁴⁰ on copper corrosion in NaCl solution. All behave as mixed type indicators.

Ravichandran *et al.* studied the influence of azoles derivatives on the corrosion of brass in sodium chloride solution⁴³⁻⁴⁵. The authors used *N*-[1-(benzotriazol-1-yl)-methyl]aniline, 1-hydroxymethylbenzotriazole, *N*-[1-(benzotriazol-1-yl)ethyl]aniline, *N,N*-dibenzotriazol-1-ylmethylaminoethane⁴⁵, *N,N*-dibenzotriazol-1-yl-aminoethane and 3-hydroxypropylbenzotriazole⁴⁴ as a corrosion inhibitors. Weight loss measurements, potentiodynamic polarization, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, cyclic voltammetry and current transient techniques were applied to analyze the effect of the organic compounds on the corrosion inhibition of brass.

Maximum inhibition efficiency was found to be 71–94% with 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} M inhibitor concentration⁴³⁻⁴⁵. These inhibitors was found to be better than benzotriazole. These are mixed type inhibitors.

Zhang *et al.*⁴¹ studied the inhibition of copper corrosion by bis-(1-benzotriazolylmethylene)-(2,5-thiadiazolyl)-disulphide in 3% NaCl and 0.5 M HCl. Potentiodynamic polarization studies indicated that the inhibitor is mixed type. Inhibition efficiency was found to be 87.6% with 10^{-3} M inhibitor concentration. The FTIR spectra indicated that the inhibitor prevented copper from corrosion by adsorption on the copper surface to form a protective complex with Cu^I ion. Sherif⁹ studied the effect of 2-amino-5-(ethylthio)-1,3,4-thiazole on copper corrosion in 3% NaCl solution using potentiodynamic polarization, potentiostatic current-time, electrochemical impedance spectroscopic, weight loss and pH measurements along with SEM and EDS investigations. Inhibition efficiency was 90% with 10^{-3} M inhibitor concentration.

Synergistic inhibition effect of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and Tween-80 on the corrosion of brass in 0.2 M NaCl solution was studied by Ramji *et al.*⁴⁶. Potentiodynamic polarization measurements showed that 2-mercaptobenzothiazole act as mixed type inhibitor and Tween-80 as an anodic inhibitor. Inhibition efficiency of 79.0 and 62.5% were obtained in the presence of optimum concentration of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and Tween-80 respectively. The addition of the mixture of these two compounds enhanced the inhibition efficiency to 94.0% and showed a synergism of inhibition. 3-Amino-1,2,4-triazole⁴⁸ inhibits both cathodic and anodic reaction indicating a mixed type inhibitor for brass in 3% NaCl solution. The inhibition efficiency reaches 98% at a concentration of 5×10^{-3} M.

A comparative electrochemical and quantum chemical calculation study²⁷ of benzotriazole and 1-hydroxybenzotriazole as copper corrosion inhibitors in 3% NaCl solution showed that benzotriazole is a more effective inhibitor than 1-hydroxybenzotriazole. Inhibition efficiency of benzotriazole is decreased in presence of S^{2-} ions due to the formation of more stable Cu-S bond than that of Cu^I benzotriazole complex⁴⁷.

Asan *et al.*⁴⁹ studied the corrosion inhibition of brass in presence of terdentate ligands, 2-[(*E*)-pyridin-2-

yliminomethyl]phenol and 2-[(pyridin-2-ylamino)-methyl]phenol in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The inhibition efficiencies increase with increasing concentration of the inhibitor. Compound containing -C=N bond gives a little bit higher inhibition efficiency. These are mixed type inhibitor. The compound 1,5-bis(μ -dithiocarboxylato-1-dodecyl-5-hydroxy-3-methyl pyrazolyl)pentane was found to be good corrosion inhibitor for copper in 3.5% sodium chloride solution. It acts as mixed type inhibitor⁵⁰.

The efficiency of 1,3-bis-diethylamino-propan-2-ol as volatile corrosion inhibitor for brass in simulated atmospheric water was studied by Gao and co-workers⁵¹. It acts as anodic inhibitor inhibition efficiency was reported to be 92.5% with 10^{-2} M inhibitor concentration. They studied the inhibition efficiencies of 1-diethylamino-propan-2-ol and 1,3-bis-diethylamino-propan-2-ol. The second compound was found to be better inhibitor. This observation was supported by density functional theoretical parameters such as the highest occupied molecule energy level (E_{HOMO}), the lowest unoccupied molecule energy level (E_{LUMO}), the energy difference (ΔE) between E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} , Mulliken charges and the HOMO orbitals⁵².

Inhibition effect of glycine derivatives on the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride was studied by Nandi and coworkers⁵³. It has been reported that the introduction of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-SO}_2\text{-}$ or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-CO}$ group increases the inhibition efficiency of glycine by 18–57% and on converting the carboxyl group into benzimidazole group the inhibition efficiency is further increased by 8–43%. *N*-Benzoylmethylbenzimidazole was found to be best inhibitor. Starting from β -alanine, they prepared 2-(β -benzosulphonamido)ethylbenzoxazole, 2-(β -benzosulphonamido)ethylbenzimidazole, 2-(β -benzosulphonamido)ethylimidazoline and 2-(β -benzosulphonamido)ethyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine and these compounds were investigated as corrosion inhibitor of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution. The inhibition efficiency was found to be increased with the increase in basic character of the compound⁵⁴. The inhibition efficiency of histidine (D_1), *N*-benzenesulphonylhistidine (D_2), *N*-benzenesulphonylhistamine (D_3), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(2-imidazolynyl)-propionic acid (D_4) and α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl)propionic acid (D_5) to-

wards the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M sodium chloride solution increase in the order : $D_1 < D_2 < D_3 < D_4 < D_5$ ⁵⁵.

Aspartic acid and glutamic acid are attractive due to the presence of more active sites. Cysteine is also very interesting amino acid that contain in addition to the amino group and caboxyl group the -SH group, which has strong affinity for copper and zinc. Nandi *et al.* studied effect of these amino acids on the corrosion of the brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution. Aspartic acid and glutamic acid are found to be better inhibitor than glycine⁵⁶ due to the presence of more active sites. Inhibition efficiency of cysteine was reported to be similar to that of glycine. They reported significant improvement in the inhibition property of aspartic acid and glutamic acid by introducing $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-SO}_2$ group⁵⁶. This may be due to the presence of π -electron of the benzene ring, introduction of electron rich $\text{SO}_2\text{-}$ group and absence of zwitterions structure⁵⁵. The inhibition efficiency of *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L(-)-glutamic acid with 4×10^{-5} M concentration was the highest (81.2–85.5%). They subsequently synthesized various derivatives, viz. α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(2-imidazolynyl)ethanoic acid, 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2-imidazolynyl)ethane⁵⁷, α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl)propanoic acid and benzene sulphonamido-1,2-bis-2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl)ethane⁵⁸ starting from *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L(-)-aspartic acid and reported further improvement in inhibition property of aspartic acid. The influence of adenine on the corrosion of copper in 1.0 M sodium chloride solution at pH 6.8 was studied by Scendo. It acts as mixed type inhibitor. The inhibition efficiency was 92% with 1×10^{-2} M adenine concentration⁵⁹.

The influence of purine on the corrosion of copper in 1 M sodium chloride solution on pH 6.8 was studied by Scendo⁶⁰. The inhibition efficiency was 97% with 5×10^{-3} M purine concentration. Purine is non-toxic and biodegradable. It acts as environmentally friendly inhibitor. Caffeine (1,3,7-trimethyl xanthine) was studied as copper corrosion inhibitor in 0.5 M KNO_3 as well as in the presence of chloride ions by Thuanny Fallavena and co-workers. The inhibition efficiency was 60% with 1.5 mM caffeine concentration⁶¹. El-Shazly *et al.* studied the corrosion of rotating copper rod in a solution of 3.5% NaCl

and 10 ppm S^{2-} ion and reported that 4-amino-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole may be effective inhibitor⁶².

Guo and co-workers used phosphates to form self-assembled monolayers in 1×10^{-3} M ethanolic solution for the inhibition of the copper corrosion in 0.2 M NaCl solution. Two types of phosphates, triethyl phosphate (TEP) and triphenyl phosphate (TPP) were used by the researcher. The best effect is achieved after 12 h immersion when the surface coverage is 93.80% for TEP, and 96.50% for TPP⁶³. When the triethyl phosphate is modified with cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, the inhibition efficiency improved markedly (99.40%)⁶⁴. External magnetic field improves the inhibition effect and the inhibition efficiency increases with the increase in the field strength. Monolayers of naturally polyphosphorylated carbohydrate on the copper surface improve its corrosion resistance in 0.1 M KCl solution⁶⁵. Patil *et al.*⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸ studied the effect of layers of poly(*o*-anisidine) and poly(*o*-toluidine) formed on copper surface on copper corrosion in 3% NaCl solution. The copolymer film of 1 : 1 *o*-anisidine and *o*-toluidine is found to be best (I.E. >99%).

Azoles are organic compounds containing nitrogen atoms with free electron pairs that are active sites for bonding with copper and that enable inhibiting action⁶⁹. Vastag and his co-workers studied thiazole derivatives as copper corrosion inhibitor in 0.1 M sodium sulphate solution. They investigated 5-benzylidene-2,4-dioxotetrahydro-1,3-thiazole (E_3); 5-(4'-isopropylbenzylidene)-2,4-dioxotetrahydro-1,3-thiazole (E_4); 5-(3'-thenylidene)-2,4-dioxotetrahydro-1,3-thiazole (E_2) and 5-(3',4'-dimethoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dioxotetrahydro-1,3-thiazole (E_1) as copper corrosion inhibitors. The inhibition efficiency order is $E_1 < E_2 < E_3 < E_4$ ⁷⁰.

Zucchi *et al.* studied the inhibiting action of tetrazole (F_1), 5-mercapto-1-methyl-tetrazole (F_4), 5-mercapto (Na-salt)-1-methyl-tetrazole (F_2), 5-mercapto-1-phenyl-tetrazole (F_5), 5-phenyl-tetrazole (F_6) and 5-amino-tetrazole (F_3) against copper corrosion in 0.1 M NaCl solution in the range of pH from 4 to 8 and at temperatures of 40 and 80 °C. The best protective characteristics are shown by F_5 and F_6 . Inhibition efficiency decreases in the following order : $F_6 > F_5 > F_4 > F_3 > F_2 > F_1$. The inhibiting action is explained by adsorption of the inhibitor on the copper surface and formation of complex with

copper⁷¹. Self-assembled monolayer of various silane derivatives are found to be good corrosion inhibitors for copper in 0.6 M NaCl solution at pH 4–10⁷²⁻⁷³. Recently corrosion inhibition of copper in 3.5% NaCl solution using 2-mercapto-4-amino-5-nitroso-6-hydroxy pyrimidine is reported⁷⁴ using various techniques. The results obtained from different corrosion evaluation techniques are in good agreement.

Curkovic *et al.*⁷⁵ reported the influence of pH on the inhibition efficiency of 4-methyl-1-phenylimidazole and 4-methyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)imidazole for copper in chloride solution. It was found that the inhibition efficiency of the reagents enhances with the increase of the solution pH value from 20% in 0.5 M HCl to 92% in 0.5 M NaCl, which was due to stronger adsorption of the neutral molecule than that of the protonated species, which may be expected in acid medium.

Hammouti and co-workers⁷⁶ studied the inhibition of copper corrosion by bipyrazole compound named *N,N*-bis(3-carbomethoxy-5-methylpyrazol-1-ylmethyl)cyclohexylamine in aerated 3% NaCl solution. The compound acts as a mixed type inhibitor and adsorbs on the copper surface according to the Langmuir isotherm model.

Ranjana and co-workers⁷⁷ studied the inhibition of *o*-aminobenzoic acid (G_1), *p*-aminobenzoic acid (G_2), *o*-benzenesulphonamidobenzoic acid (G_3), *p*-benzenesulphonamidobenzoic acid (G_4), 2-(*o*-benzenesulphonamido)phenylimidazoline (G_5), 2-(*p*-benzenesulphonamido)phenylimidazoline (G_6), 2-(*o*-benzenesulphonamido)phenyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (G_7) and 2-(*p*-benzenesulphonamido)phenyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (G_8) towards the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous solution. It has been observed that introduction of $C_6H_5-SO_2$ group increases the inhibition efficiency of aminobenzoic acid by 8–12%. When -COOH group is converted to imidazoline or 1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine group, the inhibition efficiency is further increased by 7–23%. The inhibition efficiency of these compounds increases in the order : $G_1 < G_3 < G_2 < G_5 < G_4 < G_6 < G_7 < G_8$. The inhibition efficiency of G_8 with 4×10^{-5} M concentration is the highest which reaches 95.4%. The *para* compounds are better inhibitor than the corresponding *ortho* compounds due to better surface coverage. The hydroypyrimidine derivatives are better inhibitor

than the imidazoline derivatives due to more basic character and larger size of the molecules.

Corrosion inhibition of copper and brass in alkaline solution :

Assouli *et al.*⁷⁸ studied the inhibiting action of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole on the corrosion of brass in ammonia solution (pH 6–12) by electrochemical measurements and acoustical emission technique. More than 95% inhibition efficiency was achieved using this inhibitor. Subramanian *et al.*⁷⁹ investigated the effect of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and tetrazole on corrosion of copper in 0.1 M NaOH solution. Tetrazole does not inhibit corrosion under this condition but 2-mercaptobenzothiazole acts as a corrosion inhibitor due to the formation of Cu-S bond resulting thick polymeric film. Morales *et al.*^{80–82} studied the corrosion behavior of brass at pH 9.0 with various concentration of chloride ions. They explained the passivation of brass due to the formation of the complex ZnO.H₂O/Cu₂O layer. Forsen explained⁸³ the corrosion resistance of copper and copper alloys in sea water due to the formation of protective layer containing several oxide and hydroxide phases. Corrosion studies on brass at higher pH (9–10) in presence of tetraborate indicated dezincification^{84–86}. Antonijevic *et al.* reported⁸⁷ the protective effect of benzotriazole on the corrosion of brass in alkaline solution containing varying amount of chloride and tetraborate ions. The inhibitive effect of benzotriazole is due to the formation of a stable protective film containing benzotriazole and its complex with Cu^I. Sodium phytate is reported to be effective corrosion inhibitor for brass in 0.1 M NaOH solution by Li *et al.*⁸⁸.

Conclusions

Numerous organic compounds can be used as corrosion inhibitors for copper and brass. Thiazole, benzotriazoles, benzimidazoles, imidazoles, imidazolines, tetrahydropyrimidines are good corrosion inhibitors. Adsorption of the organic molecule on the metal surface and formation of mixed ligand complex are responsible for corrosion inhibition. Compounds containing thiol group may be better inhibitor for alkaline solution. Molecular structure of the inhibitor, presence of heteroatoms (S, N, O) aromatic rings etc. in general are responsible for good inhibition efficiency. Several new inhibitors containing aromatic ring, heterocyclic ring, different hetero atom

and different coordination sites have been synthesized and attempts have been made to correlate inhibition efficiency with these factors. Intermolecular attraction is also responsible for inhibition activity. Self-assembled monolayers of inhibitor show high inhibition efficiency.

Amino acids and their derivatives are found to be promising green corrosion inhibitors. Inhibitors obtained from vegetable origin are also environmentally acceptable. Molecular modeling along with experimental work with these type of inhibitors may result development of effective green corrosion inhibitors for copper and brass.

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